

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

250,000 Years from now – Planet Mars is on a Crash Course with Planet Earth

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A Thesis in the Field of Astrophysics

NASA JPL ephemeris tables are the most interesting building block
for understanding the past and future of our Solar System.

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Newton-based Computer Algorithms take the JPL Ephemeris Tables for solar Planets to the next Level. SAMAC AG, St. Gallen

Jet Propulsion Laboratory
California Institute of Technology

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*****  
Target body name: Mars (499)                               {source: mar097}  
Center body name: Sun (10)                                 {source: DE441}  
Center-site name: BODY CENTER  
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VX= 2.466191455128526E+01 VY=-2.722160161977370E+00 VZ=-6.619819103693254E-01  
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Abstract

NASA ephemeris tables show that the orbits of our solar planets change dramatically.

This article deals with the drift, orbital velocity and inclination of the planetary orbits – tilt.

Our sources are the JPL SSD ephemerides in geometric Cartesian states. The positions of the planets are given in the format x, y, z – the orbital velocities in the format V_x, V_y, V_z .

The center of a planetary orbit is located in the middle of the main axis of an ellipse.

If \vec{P} is the position vector of a planetary perihelion and \vec{A} is the position of a planetary aphelion then $\vec{C} = (\vec{P} + \vec{A}) / 2$ is the position vector of the orbital center.

As perihelia move towards the Sun, their orbital centers and aphelia move away from the Sun.

NASA's Mars ephemerides from 1850 to 2050 show an average drift of 400 km per orbit.

The perihelia of Mars are moving closer to the Sun. – The orbital centers and aphelia of Mars are drifting away from the Sun. – SAMAC has improved the accuracy of NASA ephemerides from 1 minute to 5 seconds and developed algorithms to dig into NASA's ephemeris treasures. NASA's observations, and JPL's ephemeris software tell us which planets will be in trouble.

Our most important findings are that the orbital drift of a planet increases dramatically as its center moves further away from the sun.

The center of Mercury's orbit is about 6 million km from the Sun, while the center of Mars is 21.3 million km away from the Sun. – With an orbital period of 88 to 687 days, this results in a Mercury drift of 22 km compared to a Mars deviation of 400 km over the same time period. Mercury will have a completely different orbit in a few million years. – The drift of the Mars orbit is way more dramatic. – The minimum distance to Earth is 54 million km in 2024.

SAMAC's algorithms show that nothing will change the Martian orbit drift.

The main indicator for a Mars-Earth collision is the off-center position of the Martian orbit. SAMAC's RPVM algorithm – Rotating Parallel Vector Magnitudes – measures the PACUs – Parallel Acceleration Units – that cause the Martian drift. – It's not Jupiter. The Sun does it.

The End of Life in the Solar System

Mars will orbit the Sun 135,000 times before it crosses the orbit of our home planet.

Is there anything that can prevent the impending catastrophe?

The logical answer is: No!

The orbits of Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus and Neptune will remain outside the orbit of Mars.

The orbits of Earth, Venus and Mercury will remain within the orbit of Mars.

The gravitational forces of the Sun will be similar to those we observe in the 200 years between 1850 and 2050. The forces accompanying the current trend will therefore not reverse.

This paper shows what physicists and astronomers don't seem to be aware of – the end of life in the Solar System will occur within the astronomical blink of an eye.

This paper shows which solar object is responsible for the end of the planets Mars and Earth.

The Earth's orbit is known with an absolute precision of a few meters. – Once we know the exact orbit of one solar planet, we know the exact orbits of the other 7 planets as well.

The orbital position and velocity data are mainly based on time-of-flight measurements of radar signals reflected from the surfaces of the planets Mercury, Venus and Mars.

Several satellites have flown past, orbited or landed on all 8 planets.

The laws of celestial mechanics allow astronomers to calculate the distances and speeds.

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NASA's ephemeris tables for the Solar System show that the orbits of Mercury and Mars are both drifting towards the orbits of their nearest neighboring planets. – Mercury is drifting towards Venus. Mars is drifting towards Earth.

SAMAC has developed software algorithms to check whether the gravitational pull of the Sun and the gravitational pull of the other planets will have a similar effect in the future as shown between 1850 and 2050.

SAMAC examines *ceteris paribus* scenarios – “all other things being equal”.

1. The Sun is and remains the innermost object in the Solar System.
2. Planets will not change rank from inner planets to outer planets or vice versa.
3. There will not be an ad-hoc change of the Mercury and Mars trend without a reason.

SAMAC shows that NASA's Solar System Dynamics software can calculate more accurately.

A higher NASA accuracy will confirm what the SAMAC researchers have discovered.

The centers of Mercury's and Mars' orbits are moving away from the sun.

The orbital drifts become visible when we look at NASA's orbit-data with greater accuracy.

Between 1850 and 2050, the drift of Mercury is 2.8 km per 88-day orbit. – For Mars, we find a drift of 400 km per 687-day orbit. – These are trends based on NASA's high-precision observations and NASA's SSD software model for our Solar System.

The accelerations and decelerations of the planetary orbits cancel each other out.

The origin of the inclinations – tilts – of the planets still needs to be researched in more detail.

Higher Precision – Software Loops and Iterations

Precision in scientific investigations is important to ensure to get good results.

Galileo, 1564 to 1641, is credited with the invention of a 23x magnification telescope.

NASA planetary photo-journal

1609 Galileo discovered the Jupiter moons Io, Europa, Ganymede, and Callisto.

John Harrison, 1693 to 1776, invented the marine chronometer.

The famous Archimedes constructed sequences of polygons, that inscribed and circumscribed a unit circle, to get a lower and upper bound for a circle's circumference - which is Pi.

In 1948 Claude E. Shannon defined in mathematical terms what information is.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

When computer models represent something big, errors may be magnified into large errors.

New technologies have brought astrophysics to its current state.

We have satellites that roam our Solar System and transmit optical and radar observations to Earth at the speed of light. Researchers – amateurs and professionals – access the SSD, NASA's breathtaking online ephemeris tables on Solar System dynamics, via the Internet. The SAMAC research team has surfed extensively through the NASA ephemeris tables on the eight solar planets. – We found out what will happen to Mercury and Mars if NASA's data is trustworthy and the laws of physics are correct.

NASA's ephemeris tables give the position of the planets for every minute of time. SAMAC's Newtonian-based software algorithms can increase the accuracy of Mercury by a factor of 60 and the accuracy of Mars orbits by a factor of 12.

With this improved resolution, trends in planetary orbit shifts become visible. Will the discovered trends last forever or will the physical scenario change in the future? We are dealing with an N-body problem. – There is no simple arithmetic formula. SAMAC introduces a new artificial measure – the Rotating Parallel Vector Magnitudes RPVMs – with which we can measure how the sum of all the gravitational forces of the seven planets and the Sun correlate in total with the orbital displacement predicted in NASA's ephemeris tables.

By now at the latest, NASA's software specialists will have to admit that the floating-point accuracy of Python (15) is not sufficient for a deeper and more intelligent planetary analysis. SAMAC is working with a software genius that can provide much higher software precision.

The Authors

SAMAC AG has collected ideas, directions and corrections over a period of fifteen years. Some of our contributors have helped us by pointing out supposedly valid arguments and actual facts – and told us, where we were going wrong.

A physicist from Berlin encouraged us to analyze Mercury's orbit while she waited for her surfing lesson to begin. We discovered the treasure trove of astronomical science while surfing the internet – the NASA JPL Horizons system. – You enter a query about the location of Mercury at any given time and, if you wish, you get beautiful tables precise by the minute of where Mercury was or will be in our Solar System.

We presented our material to a well-known astronomer and asked him for help.

“These are vectors!” – Vector algebra is a part of mathematics. Vector algebra uses the algebraic operations of vector addition and scalar multiplication. – Understanding the NASA ephemeris tables as vectors was the first step for our Newton algorithms.

Mercury is between 46 million and 69 million kilometers from the Sun and moves at an orbital speed of a few dozen kilometers per second. – We wanted to calculate Mercury's perihelion precession, which is measured in arcseconds. – The NASA precision of 1-minute tables was not accurate enough. – We discovered an Excel algorithm written by David Fox that helped us determine Mercury's perihelion in second increments.

Mercury's orbit has a drift. With each orbit, its perihelia get 2.8 km closer to the Sun and its aphelia get 2.8 km closer to Venus. – In a few million years, Mercury will collide with the Sun or collide with Venus – nothing to blow an astronomer's mind.

What NASA JPL's treasure trove predicts about the future of planet Mars is shocking.

Dedication

Perhaps most of you are not hoping for miracles. The path that led to the discoveries we present here is paved with miracles. – One key moment is followed by another.

If one of the key events had gone differently, this paper would not have been written. There will be a book called “The Making Of”.

The foundation of the whole thing comes from the presenter’s mother, Regina Dittmann, and the presenter's father, Gerhardt Dittmann. They made sure that their six children went to the Gymnasium, as it is called in Germany. Once a year, the parents met with their children’s teachers for a whole day and ironed out things their kids had done in class.

Both were great communicators. Mom and Dad were a stunning couple. Dad charmed our female teachers and mom convinced our male teachers that the Dittmann kids would behave and learn better if there were any problems.

And then there's the older sister Margit. She loved to read and always had tons of books from the public library at home. Margit sparked the presenters' love of literature.

When Margit’s books were out of reach, the presenter reached for his mother’s books on ancient Egyptian and Greek mythology. – And for books on space exploration.

To find out more about the other wonders and dedications – wait for “The Making Of”.

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I. Newton based Algorithms take JPL to the next Level

NASA's ephemeris tables can be downloaded for free. – Available objects include 1,229,000+ asteroids, 3,822 comets, 211 natural satellites, all planets, the Sun, and 202 spacecraft.

Time Specification

Start time:

Stop time:

Step size: minutes

Optional, select one of the presets

- minutes
- days
- hours
- minutes
- equal intervals (unitless)
- calendar years
- calendar months

<https://ssd.jpl.nasa.gov/horizons/app.html/>

```

04 2024 - Editor
*****
Ephemeris / WWW_USER Tue Nov 14 09:04:55 2023 Pasadena, USA / Horizons
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Center body name: Sun (10) {source: DE441}
Center-site name: BODY CENTER
*****
Start time : A.D. 2024-Jan-01 00:00:00.0000 TDB
Stop time : A.D. 2025-Jan-01 00:00:00.0000 TDB
Step-size : 6 minutes
*****
Output units : KM-S
Calendar mode : Mixed Julian/Gregorian
Output type : GEOMETRIC cartesian states
Output format : 3 (position, velocity, LT, range, range-rate)
Reference frame : Ecliptic of J2000.0
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```

As tools on the researcher's and presenters' side we used MySQL and Excel.

Date	Time	x	y	z	Distance	
2024-05-08	103600	188.967.515	-83.444.992	-6.383.875	206.670.129	
2024-05-08	104200	188.971.370	-83.436.268	-6.383.786	206.670.129	Peri
2024-05-08	104800	188.975.225	-83.427.543	-6.383.698	206.670.129	

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

When we want to know the exact time, when Mars reaches its Perihelion, NASA's query will give us a precision of 1 Minute of orbit-time. – If we want to be more precise, we can use an algorithm provided by David Fox based on Newton's inertia formulas.

NASA gives us ephemerides tables in vector format. \vec{P} is a vector, that describes where Mars is within a cartesian solar frame, and \vec{V} describes Mars' orbit velocity and its 3D heading.

Without solar or planetary gravity Mars would reach a new position \vec{P}_{n+x} after x seconds

$$\text{where } \vec{P}_{n+x} = \vec{P} + y * \vec{V}.$$

“This Excel program simulates orbital motion, by propagating iterated straight-line motion over short time intervals, from an initial position and velocity, using Newton's Law of Gravitation and mechanical equations. The central body is located at the origin, and the coordinate system is such that the X-Y plane is equatorial – the X-axis may be regarded as pointing toward the Vernal Equinox – with the Z-axis pointing north.” David Fox

G (N·m²/kg²) =	6,674255E-11	M (kg) =	1,98875E+30	m (kg) =	6,41799E+23	Δt (s) =	5
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G is the gravitational constant, M is the mass of the sun, and m is the mass of Mars.

JPL ephemeris tables provide position vectors and velocity vectors for the 8 solar planets.

JPL's precision limits are 1 minute time increments. Fox' Excel interpolates orbit curves starting with a positional vector (x₀, y₀, z₀) and a velocity vector (V_{x0}, V_{y0}, V_{z0}).

m I is the mass of the orbiting body – here Mars. – Δ t (s) is the time increment in seconds.

X0 (m)	Y0 (m)	Z0 (m)
188,967,515,194	-83,444,992,098	-6,383,874,593

This is the positional vector of Mars when it is close to its perihelion at time t₀.

Vx (m/s)	Vy (m/s)	Vz (m/s)	V (m/s)
10,710	24,234	245	26,496

This is the velocity vector of Mars when it is close to its perihelion at time t₀.

The gravitational pull of the Sun is 1,99E+21 Newton at this point.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Mars is accelerated with (a_x -0,0028; a_y 0,0013; a_z 0,0001; total 0,0031) m/s².

The actual velocity and the acceleration move Mars to new position (x_1, y_1, z_1).

The new time t_1 is $t_0 + 5$ seconds.

The actual velocity and the acceleration give Mars a new velocity vector (V_{x1}, V_{y1}, V_{z1}).

Because of JPL's Python software-language floating-point (15) limit,

David Fox can improve NASA's 1 minute accuracy for Mars to a 5 seconds precision.

This is how we handled the millions of Mars ephemeris rows in Excel.

In phase I we identify the days, when Mars is closest to the Sun – perihelia.

One Mars orbit takes 687 days. We get 106 complete orbits and 106 perihelia positions.

In phase II we reduce our search within each orbit on 48 hours in 6 minutes steps.

In phase III we fill the start minute and the end minute with the respective positions and velocities from the NASA ephemeris tables into the David Fox algorithm.

2024-05-08	10:42:00	480	206.670.129
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The Mars perihelion in 2024 will have a distance to the Sun of 206.670.129 km,

and it will happen on May 8th at 10:42:00 TDB time + 480 seconds.

With the same method we did find the aphelia of the 106 Mars orbits we have investigated.

The aphelia and the center of the Mars orbits drift away from the Sun.

The Earth orbits do show next to no drift, compared to the drift of Mars.

The SAMAC analysis shows that Mars has an average 402 km drift per orbit.

The Martian perihelia drifting closer to the Earth-orbit.

The mini-planet Pluto's orbit has a tilt 15 degrees toward the solar plane. This is typical for

Kuiper belt objects. The angles of the solar planets in 2024 are: Mercury 6.34° – Venus 2.19°

Earth 1.57° – Mars 1.67° – Jupiter 0.32° – Saturn 0.93° – Uranus 1.02° – Neptune 0.72°.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

The main axis of the mars-orbit gets 7,35 km wider with every orbit.

Both – the drift of the Mars' orbit and the growth of the main axis of the orbit –
must be subject to further investigations.

II. The Magnitude of the Solar System and the Planets

A trip to Mars takes seven to nine months and about 480 million kilometers.

A round-trip would take about 21 months. You will need to wait about three months on Mars to make sure Earth and Mars are in a suitable location to make the trip back home

	Mars	Earth
Max. orbital velocity (km/s)	26.50	30.29
Min. orbital velocity (km/s)	21.97	29.29

The M16 rifle fires bullets of 55-gram bullets with a velocity of 0.99 km/s.

The mass of Mars is $0.64 * 10^{24}$ kg. – The mass of Earth is $5.97 * 10^{24}$ kg.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

To be able to navigate in the Solar System we have to sharpen our senses.

We have to find numbers, which we can relate to. – Let us look at the solar planets.

The acceleration the Earth exerts on people at sea level, also called G-force or g, is a good start, when we want to get an understanding of what makes the Solar System tick.

Earth's gravity is what keeps you on the ground and what makes things fall.

The gravity on Earth is Earth 9.81 m/s^2 – when we ignore the rotation of the Earth.

The gravity on Mars is 3.71 m/s^2 . – In this context gravity is the acceleration the main body exerts on a small body with the small body close to the surface of the huge body.

NASA's Mars robots Ingenuity and Perseverance. – Photo courtesy of Kurt Hickman

Ingenuity is a small autonomous NASA 1.8 kilograms helicopter operating on Mars.

Perseverance is a 1,025 kg car-sized rover exploring Mars as part of NASA's 2020 mission.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

The g-force of a massive object can be calculated by using a formula derived from

Isaac Newton's law of gravity. $F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$, $G = 6.67 \times 10^{-11}$

The formula for the g-force is

$$g = \frac{Gm}{r^2}$$

G = gravitational Constant, m = mass of object, r = distance from center of object.

gs Sun exerts on planet $\frac{m}{s^2}$			Distance to Sun in Million km		
	Perihelion	Aphelion	Perihelion	Aphelion	Orbit Center
Mercury	0,0627	0,0272	Mercury	46,0	11,9
Venus	0,0115	0,0112	Venus	107,5	0,7
Earth	0,006134	0,005737	Earth	147,1	2,5
Mars	0,003108	0,002136	Mars	206,7	21,3
Jupiter	0,000242	0,000199	Jupiter	741	38
Saturn	0,000072	0,000058	Saturn	1.358	74
Uranus	0,000018	0,000015	Uranus	2.733	134
Neptune	0,000007	0,000006	Neptune	4.471	44


```

python 15 Decimals
# Python 3: Fibonacci series up to n
>>> def fib(n):
>>>     a, b = 0, 1
>>>     while a < n:
>>>         print(a, end=' ')
>>>         a, b = b, a+b
>>>     print()
>>> fib(1000)
0 1 1 2 3 5 8 13 21 34 55 89 144 233 377 610 987
    
```

NASA's software-bottleneck is Python's floating-point limit of 15 decimals.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

The movement of the 8 planets around our Sun is predictable – but only over an astronomically short period of time. – Astronomers think in terms of billions of years when they talk about the time when the solar system began to exist.

They think in millions of years when they describe huge meteorite impacts such as the Chicxulub impact that led to the extinction of the dinosaurs.

NASA JPL's ephemerides tell us that the perihelion of Mars will be only 150 million km from the Sun in about 250 thousand years. – Wait a minute! – Planet Earth has a perihelion of 147 million kilometers and an aphelion of 152 million kilometers.

NASA's solar ephemeris tables are based on physical observations.

Internally, NASA's computer programs minimize the errors.

Python's floating-point accuracy of 15 digits is great when it comes to multiplying numbers.

However, when adding large and small numbers, important information can be lost. External software subroutines are routines that are created separately from the program that calls them. Add-ins are software programs that extend the capabilities of other programs.

SAMAC recommends the use of high-precision add-ins for Python applications.

We have gigantic distances between the planets and the sun, huge orbital speeds and accelerations down to the micrometer range – SAMAC recommends an accuracy of 30+.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

As humans, we are in the middle between tiny and huge, between chaos and fixed rules.

The laws of Kepler and Newton are crystal clear. When we look at the solar system and the universe, which are governed by Kepler's and Newton's laws, almost all of us are lost.

The Sun has a weight of $1.989 \text{ E}30 \text{ kg}$. We can only write these numbers in exponential form.

The gravitational constant is $6.6743 * 10\text{E-}11 \text{ m}^3 / (\text{kg s}^2)$. – There are very few people in this world who can really understand what they are doing when they play around with it.

We understand days, minutes and seconds, but imagine that light travels more than a billion kilometers per hour. – To accurately calculate the rotation – the “precession” – of Mercury, we need to track Mercury's orbit in 1-second increments, which is 86,400 seconds per day.

We've tried to make some of the numbers we're talking about understandable for laypeople.

III. NASA's Ephemeris Tables: Martian Orbit Drift and Earth's stable Orbit

In Astronomy Ephemeris Tables tell the truth.

Orbit #	Date	Time	+ Seconds	Distance Mars to Sun	Orbit #	Date	Time	+ Seconds	Distance Mars to Sun	Orbit #	Date	Time	+ Seconds	Distance Mars to Sun
001	1851-04-22	235400	340	206.676.813	041	1926-07-18	153000	435	206.658.829	081	2001-10-12	072400	525	206.656.461
002	1853-03-09	203000	500	206.702.473	042	1928-06-04	190600	215	206.677.470	082	2003-08-30	110600	280	206.616.683
003	1855-01-25	174800	220	206.681.199	043	1930-04-22	124800	385	206.680.304	083	2005-07-17	154200	290	206.639.036
004	1856-12-12	214800	370	206.687.305	044	1932-03-09	140600	515	206.636.523	084	2007-06-04	123600	495	206.666.409
005	1858-10-30	163000	240	206.699.377	045	1934-01-25	184800	415	206.651.519	085	2009-04-21	094800	320	206.644.761
006	1860-09-16	171200	370	206.650.448	046	1935-12-13	162400	490	206.682.700	086	2011-03-09	140600	415	206.651.228
007	1862-08-04	230000	540	206.656.228	047	1937-10-30	123000	415	206.665.622	087	2013-01-24	090000	235	206.668.403
008	1864-06-21	223000	335	206.693.646	048	1939-09-17	173000	415	206.658.068	088	2014-12-12	083000	210	206.626.584
009	1866-05-09	174800	215	206.686.554	049	1941-08-04	140600	325	206.683.157	089	2016-10-29	131200	425	206.630.988
010	1868-03-26	210000	350	206.672.488	050	1943-06-22	123000	365	206.644.154	090	2018-09-16	125400	355	206.660.725
011	1870-02-11	184800	210	206.702.138	051	1945-05-09	172400	250	206.639.602	091	2020-08-03	090600	245	206.651.397
012	1871-12-30	150600	340	206.666.315	052	1947-03-27	171800	390	206.672.499	092	2022-06-21	130600	450	206.640.203
013	1873-11-16	195400	200	206.651.028	053	1949-02-11	124800	450	206.671.512	093	2024-05-08	104200	480	206.670.129
014	1875-10-04	211800	385	206.680.835	054	1950-12-30	151800	395	206.652.613	094	2026-03-26	071200	195	206.633.188
015	1877-08-21	173000	435	206.687.320	055	1952-11-16	144800	520	206.684.646	095	2028-02-11	121200	470	206.618.707
016	1879-07-09	191200	460	206.665.008	056	1954-10-04	101800	480	206.654.308	096	2029-12-29	131800	290	206.654.285
017	1881-05-26	204200	220	206.695.884	057	1956-08-21	153000	290	206.628.929	097	2031-11-16	080600	510	206.661.347
018	1883-04-13	143600	255	206.680.311	058	1958-07-09	183000	535	206.661.467	098	2033-10-03	091800	195	206.631.210
019	1885-02-28	175400	445	206.646.112	059	1960-05-26	140600	220	206.678.303	099	2035-08-21	113600	285	206.656.551
020	1887-01-16	211800	490	206.671.773	060	1962-04-13	130600	440	206.651.049	100	2037-07-08	065400	290	206.642.476
021	1888-12-03	174200	205	206.693.905	061	1964-02-29	161200	350	206.670.646	101	2039-05-26	102400	190	206.611.294
022	1890-10-21	153600	485	206.667.498	062	1966-01-16	101800	480	206.668.342	102	2041-04-12	133600	380	206.637.801
023	1892-09-07	204800	285	206.676.088	063	1967-12-04	121800	400	206.629.729	103	2043-02-28	095400	490	206.660.988
024	1894-07-26	154800	290	206.686.521	064	1969-10-21	162400	435	206.647.048	104	2045-01-15	074200	440	206.639.039
025	1896-06-12	163600	460	206.646.853	065	1971-09-08	143000	360	206.672.764	105	2046-12-03	112400	225	206.651.129
026	1898-04-30	210600	310	206.657.779	066	1973-07-26	114200	200	206.653.496	106	2048-10-20	053600	490	206.658.200
027	1900-03-18	191200	205	206.688.890	067	1975-06-13	160600	530	206.656.283	107	2050-09-07	071200	450	206.611.490
028	1902-02-03	150000	400	206.675.900	068	1977-04-30	112400	225	206.675.538					
029	1903-12-22	184800	505	206.667.356	069	1979-03-18	102400	275	206.631.342					
030	1905-11-08	153000	360	206.693.801	070	1981-02-02	154800	370	206.633.342					
031	1907-09-26	132400	245	206.650.241	071	1982-12-21	150600	480	206.670.430					
032	1909-08-13	191200	460	206.640.902	072	1984-11-07	101200	395	206.665.894					
033	1911-07-01	203000	405	206.679.225	073	1986-09-25	134200	360	206.644.634					
034	1913-05-18	152400	310	206.684.443	074	1988-08-12	130600	210	206.674.787					
035	1915-04-05	164200	365	206.660.053	075	1990-06-30	093000	305	206.644.699					
036	1917-02-20	172400	310	206.688.334	076	1992-05-17	140600	250	206.625.041					
037	1919-01-08	121200	515	206.666.897	077	1994-04-04	154200	465	206.656.482					
038	1920-11-25	161800	180	206.638.201	078	1996-02-20	111800	500	206.667.706					
039	1922-10-13	191800	510	206.664.658	079	1998-01-07	112400	430	206.643.630					
040	1924-08-30	161800	405	206.682.477	080	1999-11-25	133000	190	206.669.029					

SAMAC did improve the accuracy of the NASA ephemeris tables from 1 minute to 5 seconds – SAMAC, using Newton-based algorithms.

These ephemeris tables are based on NASA's JPL Horizons software.

NASA is the most reliable source on solar planets and their orbits.

NASA has rovers traveling on Mars and satellites orbiting Mars.

NASA's position and orbit information about Mars is based on radar measurements.

Our approach is simple. – Anyone with a high school diploma can recreate it.

Upon request, we are happy to share what we downloaded from NASA

and what methods and algorithms we used.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

The trend of Mars drifting 400 km per orbit becomes visible when the accuracy of the NASA ephemeris tables has been increased by a factor of 12 – the NASA tables have an accuracy of 1 minute per planetary position.

The SAMAC-Newton algorithm for Mars shows 5-second increments.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

This simple Excel chart shows that the perihelia of Mars are approaching the sun.

At the same time and at about the same speed, the aphelion of Mars drifts away from the Sun.

We will show that the Sun's gravity is the cause. Nothing can stop the Sun's gravitational pull.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

While Mars drifts towards Jupiter on one side of its orbit and towards the Earth's orbit on the opposite side, the Earth's orbit tends to become more circular.

IV. Planet Mars on Crash Course with Earth

According to NASA JPL's ephemeris tables, the planet Mars is on a crash course with Earth. The perihelion of Mars today is 206 million km from the sun. – The perihelion of Mars moves an average of 400 km closer to the Sun with each orbit. NASA's ephemeris tables on the orbits of Mars between 1850 and 2050 show this trend. – In 250,000 years, the perihelion of Mars' orbits will be only 150 million km away from the sun.

The orbit of our Earth has a perihelion of 147 million km and an aphelion of 152 million km.

This work shows that the drift of Mars of 400 km per orbit is caused by the gravitational forces exerted on Mars by the other solar planets.

If humans do not intervene, life on Earth will end when Mars and Earth get too close.

250,000 years is less than the blink of an eye on the astronomical scale.

We cannot force Mars out of its orbit. We cannot blow up Mars. – We have to wipe it out.

Our only chance is to orbit Mars with giant mirrors and vaporize it completely with solar-powered lasers. Perhaps 250,000 years is enough time to accomplish this gigantic task.

The accuracy of NASA's ephemeris tables must and can be improved.

Nevertheless, Mars appears to be curved. Is the orbital drift of Mars caused by other planets?

V. The Common Sense Approach

The JPL ephemeris tables show the solar system in a Cartesian (x, y, z) frame.

The Sun is placed in the center with the coordinates (0, 0, 0).

The plane of the Sun is set to (-149 million km, 0 km, 0 km) at the vernal equinox of the earth. The z-values for all points on the solar plane are zero.

The z-coordinates of the planet's position vectors oscillate around the solar plane.

On March 20, 2000 at 07:00 TDB. the Earth was at (-149 million km, 47,500 km, -183 km).

March 20 to 21, the Earth has its vernal equinox, when day and night are of equal length.

The orbit of each solar planet can be compared to a giant Frisbee ring.

When one part of the frisbee approaches the sun, the point on the other side of the frisbee is pushed away from the sun. The planetary orbits have a drift, a spin and a tilt.

All planets move counterclockwise around the centers of their respective orbits.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Planetary orbits can drift their center away from the sun.

Planetary orbits can have a precession.

Planetary orbits can be tilted towards the solar plane.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Our development tool is Microsoft Excel. Our graphics are created with MS PowerPoint and MS Excel. The data we use for our research is produced by NASA JPL's Horizons system.

Everyone has free access to the knowledge and data of the JPL solar system.

Horizons System

ssd.jpl.nasa.gov/horizons/app.html#/

Home

Home / Tools / Horizons System

Save/Load Settings...

1 Ephemeris Type: Vector Table

2 Edit Target Body: Mercury

3 Edit Coordinate Center: Sun (body center) [500@10]

4 Edit Time Specification: Start=2022-09-21 TDB Step=1 (minutes)

5 Edit Table Settings: ecliptic x-y plane

geometric states

km and seconds

<https://ssd.jpl.nasa.gov/horizons/app.html#/>

Horizons creates CSV files that anyone can download to their computer.

Generate Ephemeris

Ephemeris Results

Download Results

We will share SAMAC's VBA algorithms on how to convert JPL's CSVs into Excel.

VI. Trends only change if there is an important reason for them.

The red line shows an upward trend. In January, the measures taken by the Department of Health and Human Services – HHS – turn the trend into a downward trend for a few weeks. The pattern from March onwards looks like an upward and downward trend.

“Trend analysis is a quantitative study of what happens over a period of time. It involves collecting data from multiple time periods and plotting the information on a line chart for further analysis.” study.com – “The three main types of trends are upward trends, downward trends and horizontal trends.” Indeed.com

“Rabbits were introduced to Australia in the 18th century and as there were no natural predators, their population exploded. In the 1950s, a virus called myxoma was introduced, which led to a collapse in the population.” – nau.edu

This downward trend ended, when the surviving rabbits developed immunity.

“Ceteris paribus” in Latin means “all other things being equal”

“This concept can be used to explain natural or scientific laws as well as economic theories. For example, imagine testing the law of gravity. – If you throw an apple from the top of a tree, it will fall to the ground, assuming there are no changes in normal circumstances or ‘ceteris paribus’ – but what if a freak storm passes by and a tornado takes the apple with it? That’s an example of how things are not the same.” – GoCardless

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

We use the **International System of Units**, which is the modern form of the metric system.

SI base units

Symbol	Name	Quantity
s	second	time
m	metre	length
kg	kilogram	mass
A	ampere	electric current
K	kelvin	thermodynamic temperature
mol	mole	amount of substance
cd	candela	luminous intensity

CODATA is the Data Committee of the International Science Council – ISC.

CODATA promotes global collaboration to improve the availability and usability of data for all areas of research. If no CODATA values are available, we use the JPL page of NASA.

The positions, directions and velocities of the planets are downloaded from NASA JPL.

Our position vectors and velocity vectors are calculated in 3D.

When we use 2D graphics, they are a compressed version of 3D reality.

We use the best sources to get information about the solar system and its planets.

We use basic software technologies that every high school graduate should know and understand. – We look for trends and patterns in JPL Horizon’s solar data palace.

VII. SAMAC's RPVM Software Algorithm

“The term g- ‘force’ is technically incorrect, as it is a measure of acceleration, not force.

While acceleration is a vector quantity, accelerations with g-force – ‘g-forces’ for short – are often expressed as a scalar based on the vector magnitude.” WIKIPEDIA

“This aerobatic aircraft pulls upwards in a +g manoeuvre; the pilot experiences an inertial acceleration of several g in addition to gravity. Due to the cumulative forces of the vertical axis acting on his body, he currently 'weighs' many times more than normal.” WIKIPEDIA

Definition: 1 ACU is the acceleration that a body experiences in space due to another body.

On October 6, 2024 at 01:00:00 UTC, the inner planets will have the above constellation.

Before 1972, UTC time was called Greenwich Mean Time – GMT – and is now referred to as Coordinated Universal Time or Universal Time Coordinated UTC. – It is a coordinated time scale developed by the Bureau International des Poids et Mesures – BIPM.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Mars ACUs are: Sun 2,60E-03 – Mercury 2,86E-10 – Venus 3,05E-09 – Earth 1,24E-08 –
 Jupiter 2,47E-07 – Saturn – 2,24E-08 – Uranus 8,04E-10 – Neptune 3,57E-10

The accelerations are directed from Mars to the sun and the planets.

The planets and the sun pull Mars in all possible directions. – Very confusing.

The positions of the planets are constantly changing – the ACUs and angles of attack change.

Definition: 1 PACU – Parallel Acceleration Unit – is an artificial unit for measuring the ACUs at a given time between an object in space and a given vector.

Example 1:

We want to measure how strongly Jupiter accelerates Mars towards the Martian perihelion at 01:00:00 on October 6, 2024.

Distance between Mars and Jupiter	999 Mio km
Mass of Jupiter	1.898E+27 kg
Force	8.30E+15 Newton
ACU	1.27E-07 m / sec ²

Angle between Perihelion Vector and Gravitation 85.8 degrees

$$\text{PACU}_{\text{Perihelion}} = \cos(85.8) * \text{ACU} = 9.25\text{E-}09 \text{ m / sec}^2$$

Jupiter pulls the Martian Perihelion away from the Sun.

Angle between Perihelion Vector and Orbit Velocity 85.8 degrees

$$\text{PACU}_{\text{Orbit Velocity}} = \cos(78.1) * \text{ACU} = 2.62\text{E-}08 \text{ m / sec}^2$$

Jupiter accelerates Mars on its orbit.

Example 2:

We want to measure how strongly Jupiter accelerates Mars on April 4, 2025 at 01:00:00 in the direction of the Mars perihelion of this orbit.

Distance between Mars and Jupiter	1,245 Mio km
Mass of Jupiter	1.898E+27 kg
Force	5.35E+15 Newton
ACU	8.17E-08 m / sec ²

Angle between Perihelion Vector and Gravitation 85.8 degrees

$$\text{PACU}_{\text{Perihelion}} = \cos(70.2) * \text{ACU} = 2.77\text{E-}08 \text{ m / sec}^2$$

Jupiter pulls the Martian Perihelion away from the Sun.

Angle between Perihelion Vector and Orbit Velocity 85.8 degrees

$$\text{PACU}_{\text{Orbit Velocity}} = \cos(172.6) * \text{ACU} = -8.11\text{E-}08 \text{ m / sec}^2$$

Jupiter decelerates Mars on its orbit.

The PACUs allow us to understand, how gravitational forces can cancel each other out.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

A vector is a term used in mathematics and physics. Vectors have two different properties: magnitude and direction. The direction of a vector runs from its end to its head.

The magnitude is a scalar, which is given as a length.

The component of the force in the direction of movement is the length of the line AB.

Using the rule for a right-angled triangle $\cos \theta = \frac{\text{adjacent}}{\text{hypotenuse}}$.

The length of AB is $F \times \cos \theta$.

Resolving the force in the direction of motion is finding this value.

“Inertia is a property of matter by which it remains at rest or in uniform motion in the same straight line unless acted upon by an external force”.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Gravity has a direction that determines where a body is pulled. – The RPVM algorithm is a kind of inversion of the parallelogram method in that it splits the gravitational vector into sub-vectors, each of which has a specific effect on the body. – We only measure the part of the gravitational force that is parallel to a given situation. – We measured the acceleration of the Sun and the other 7 planets on (a) Mercury and (b) Mars. – NASA’s ephemeris tables tell us how the perihelia of Mercury and Mars are moving, their direction of motion at a given time and their altitude (z) above the plane of the Sun. – Parallel acceleration can be summarized. The planets do not revolve around the Sun – they revolve around the center of an ellipse in which the Sun is one of the two focal points. – The gravitational pull of the Sun and the other planets has this effect on each of the other planets, as we see here for Mars:

One component that draws the perihelion of Mars parallel along a line from its perihelion of 1851 to the position where Mars' perihelion will be in 2048.

One component, that accelerates or decelerates the velocity of the Martian orbit.

One component, that pulls Mars’ orbit towards or away from the solar plane.

$$g = \frac{Gm}{r^2}$$

is an acceleration Vector.

We use the acceleration vectors, because we can relate to the magnitude of the acceleration.

Is Mars’ orbit a death spiral, no matter what – or are his neighbor planets the trouble-makers?

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

We present a new artificial measuring instrument – the SAMAC RPVMs.

The gravitational pull of the Sun and each planet has a direct influence on the other planets.

There is no arithmetic formula, because we are dealing with an n-body problem.

The gravitational forces between the planets and the sun, the positions and the orbits of the planets can easily be calculated in vector form. What do we look for first and foremost?

The center of Mars' orbit moved along a line from 1851 to 2048.

The amounts of the parallel vectors can be added and subtracted to obtain the total amount.

All planets orbit around the center of their ellipses. Using the SAMAC RPVM algorithms, we can filter out what amount of a particular gravitational acceleration vector pulls the center of Mars from its position in 1851 to its position in 2048.

To understand what certain PACUs mean, SAMAC has created a series of cockpits that we will be happy to share in detail with interested researchers and the public.

ACUs are acceleration units exerted by a gravitational body on another body. The Earth's average gravitational pull is 9.807 meters per second squared – m/s^2 . The gravitational acceleration exerted by the Sun on Mercury is 0.0625 m/s^2 at Mercury's perihelion and 0.0272 at Mercury's aphelion. The corresponding ACUs for Mars are 0.0031 and 0.0021.

These gravitational forces can be divided into components that are (A) parallel to the line from Mercury to the Sun, (B) parallel to the direction Mercury is heading at a given time, and (C) a component that is perpendicular to Mercury's altitude above or below the plane of the Sun. – Parallel vectors can be added together or subtracted.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Mathematicians and physicists use vectors to represent and calculate positions, velocities, accelerations and the pull of gravity. – And all sorts of things.

Vectors are a fabulous tool for astrophysics. Vectors make it easy to calculate distances between two points in a 3D space (x_1, y_1, z_1) and (x_2, y_2, z_2) .

$$r = \text{sqrt} ((x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2)$$

Remember? – The good old Greek, Mr. Pythagoras.

The (a) vectors have the same direction, but a different magnitude. (b) Vectors point in different directions, but have the same magnitude. We use vectors to measure the distance between the Sun and the planets, and between one planet and another.

Rotational Parallel Vector Magnitudes – RPVMS – measure the gravitational forces that the other planets exert on Mercury's orbit, depending on the distance to the Sun (A), the speed of Mercury on its orbit (B) and how strongly the other planets pull Mercury towards or away from the plane of the Sun (C). – The planets in our solar system revolve around the Sun – our central body. Mercury is in the innermost orbit. – When Jupiter has completed 1 orbit, Mercury has completed 48 orbits. – Mercury orbits the Sun 4 x 30 times, i.e. 120 times, for each orbit by Saturn. Uranus orbits the Sun within 84 years. Neptune orbits the Sun within 165 years. – The orbital ratio between Mercury and Earth is 4.15 and with Venus 2.56.

Calculating Rotational Parallel Vector Magnitudes, RPVMs, is a simple process once you understand the concept. We have downloaded data from Horizons.

The goal is to measure the influence of seven planets on a planet's orbit.

Since the Mercury orbit puzzle has become the cornerstone of the standard model of physics, we focus on analysing Mercury's orbit.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Time	Mercury	Sun	P 02	P 03	P 04	P 05	P 06	P 07	P 08
yyyy mm dd hh mm ss	x, y, z	Vx, Vy, Vz	S, V, P	S, V, P	S, V, P	S, V, P	S, V, P	S, V, P	S, V, P
	x, y, z	Mercury's position			S = +/- acceleration to sun				
	Vx, Vy, Vz	Mercury's orbit velocity			V = +/- acceleration to orbit				
					P = +/- acceleration to solar plane				
P 02 = Venus, P 03 = Earth, P 04 Mars, P05 Jupiter, P06 = Saturn, P07 = Uranus, P 08 = Neptune									

We are now entering the field of spreadsheets and vector algebra. MS Excel is easy to program. Vector formulas are as simple as you can imagine. – It's like 7th grade.

Horizons gives us the position data, the masses of the Sun and the eight planets as well as the speed of Mercury and the direction in which it is moving at any given time.

We know the positions of the individual planets and the sun, and with good accuracy the mass of the Sun and all the planets. The gravitational constant is also well known.

Let's take a look at Mercury's first perihelion in 2023. – This perihelion will take place on January 2 at 20:17:34. – Based on NASA data.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

The position of all planets at this date and time. Let's calculate how strongly each planet pulls Mercury away from or closer to the Sun. – The Sun's gravitational pull on Mercury is blue.

The gravitational pull of Venus is red. M's orbit is green.

The Sun's accelerates M by 0.063 m/sec^2 .

The Mercury acceleration of Venus is $0.00000018 \text{ m/sec}^2$. Venus pulls Mercury in the direction of the sun. If we include the angle of attack of this total force, we realize that only 43% of it is in play. A large part of the force slows down the orbital speed of Mercury.

We do the same calculations for Earth, Mars and Jupiter and see what happens.

Blue is the pull of the Sun on Mercury, red is the pull of Earth, green Mercury's orbit.

Earth accelerates M with a total of $0.00000035 \text{ m/sec}^2$. – Earth pulls M away from the Sun. –

We include the angle of attack of that total force and see 93 % is in play.

A minor part of that total accelerates Mercury's orbit velocity.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Blue is the pull of the Sun on Mercury, red is the pull of Mars, green Mercury's orbit.

Mars accelerates M with a total pull of $0.000000012 \text{ m/sec}^2$. Mars pulls M away from the Sun. We include the angle of attack of that total acceleration and see 98 % is in play.

A minimal part of that total accelerates M's orbit velocity.

Finally, Jupiter. Jupiter is by far the biggest planet in the solar system, about 1/1000 of the mass of the Sun, and way bigger than the other seven planets.

Le Verrier and his followers will tell you that Jupiter has the greatest influence on the orbits of the other planets. They haven't heard of the legend of the ghost ship. It's full of dead pirates, their slain victims and tons of gold and jewels. – Sad Mary never comes ashore. Some adventurers have managed to get on board. With a favourable wind, they set sail.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

The next morning, they discovered that the Sad Mary had returned to the same place where she had disembarked the day before. The wind direction had changed overnight, blowing the Sad Mary back to where she had come from.

The same phenomenon happened to Jupiter's gravity when it began to pull on Mercury. Mercury is pulled towards or away from the Sun by Jupiter. – The Sad Mary effect sets in after about 44 days – when Mercury has travelled half its distance around the Sun. – Where Jupiter previously pulled, it now pushes. Jupiter pushed before. Now it is pulling.

He cancels himself out.

The gravitational forces of the Sun and the planets are gigantic. Nevertheless, the acceleration they cause per second of Mercury's orbit is incredibly small. A Mercury orbit lasts between 7,600,157 seconds and 7,600,951 seconds, measured from perihelion to the next perihelion. – We use our RPVM method to calculate a statistical sum of the push and pull forces. We calculate Mercury's attractive and repulsive forces with respect to the Sun and also how much Jupiter is accelerating and decelerating the speed of Mercury's orbit.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Blue is the gravitational pull of the Sun on Mercury, red is the gravitational pull of Jupiter, green is the orbital direction of Mercury. – Jupiter accelerates Mercury with a total acceleration of $0.00000243 \text{ m/sec}^2$. Jupiter pulls M away from the sun. If we include the angle of attack of this total acceleration, we see that 43% of it is in play. A large part of this total acceleration slows down the orbital velocity of M.

These diagrams show Jupiter's gravitational RPVMs for Mercury's orbit starting on January 1, 2023 and ending on March 31, 2023. The accelerations are summed up.

Depending on Jupiter's distance from Mercury and the angle, Jupiter's gravitational pull can reach an acceleration of 20 cm/sec^2 RPVM per day, or 86,400 seconds.

After 7,600,538 seconds, the sum of Jupiter's RPVM is close to zero.

Mercury's perihelion precession is 1.15 arcseconds for this orbit. Below we show a planetary fact sheet. The distance between the planet Earth and the main body of our solar system, the Sun, is between 147 and 152 million km.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

	mass of Planet kg	min Distance in m	max Distance in m	max Force in Newton	min Force in Newton	max gs	min gs
Mercury	3.30E+23	4.60E+10	6.98E+10	2.07E+22	8.99E+21	0.00639523	0.00277754
Venus	4.87E+24	1.07E+11	1.09E+11	5.64E+22	5.44E+22	0.00118196	0.00113899
Earth	6.05E+24	1.47E+11	1.52E+11	3.71E+22	3.47E+22	0.00062546	0.00058498
Mars	6.42E+23	2.06E+11	2.49E+11	2.01E+21	1.37E+21	0.00031889	0.00021826
Jupiter	1.90E+27	7.41E+11	8.17E+11	4.59E+23	3.77E+23	0.00002465	0.00002027
Saturn	5.68E+26	1.43E+12	1.50E+12	3.67E+22	3.34E+22	0.00000659	0.00000599
Uranus	8.68E+25	2.74E+12	3.00E+12	1.54E+21	1.28E+21	0.00000180	0.00000150
Neptune	1.02E+26	4.46E+12	4.55E+12	6.85E+20	6.58E+20	0.00000068	0.00000065

CGPM, the General Conference on Weights and Measures, has declared the second, meter, kilogram, ampere, kelvin, mole and candela to be the official physical standard units.

Our min-max g-accelerations in the table above are our final official calculations.

The acceleration due to gravity on the surface of the Moon is about 1.625 m/s^2 .

The average gravitational acceleration on Mars is 3.72076 m/s^2 .

Jupiter is the largest and most massive planet in the solar system.

The gravitational force on the surface of Jupiter, at the cloud tops, is 24.79 m/s^2 or 2.528 g.

The orbital speed of the planet Earth is between 105 and 109 thousand km per hour.

The solar g-s that keep us in orbit range from 0.000585 to 0.0006255 m/s^2 .

These are numbers.

Huge forces, crazy speeds, huge masses and tiny accelerations. We are much better off today than Monsieur Le Verrier was in 1860 – then telescopes, now James Webb.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

NASA's James Webb Space Telescope is an infrared space observatory that was launched on in 2021. The JWST is 100 times more powerful than Hubble. Its infrared lens looks further into the depths of the universe. The James Webb Space Telescope has travelled a distance of 1.5 million kilometers to its final location: Lagrange point 2.

Lagrange point 2 is a gravitationally stable location in space, 2nd Sun-Earth Lagrange point.

VIII. Ceteris Paribus Scenario – Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy

Ceteris paribus is of great importance in analyzes, statements, experiments or theories if their validity is made dependent on the unchanged existence of the boundary conditions.

“Hootie is a good dog as long as there is no thunderstorm and no squirrels get through.”

Ceteris paribus is a Latin term meaning "all else being equal" and is the opposite of the Latin expression mutatis mutandis, which means "after all changes". Mathematically, the expression means that all variables are held constant in order to observe the effects of a single independent variable on a dependent variable.

We have observed that the perihelia of Mars are drifting towards the Sun.

We are analyzing what the gravitational forces will do in the future with Mars.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

“Natural laws are at the center of the philosophy of science and metaphysics.

Laws are usually assumed to be closely related to many key philosophical concepts such as causality, explanation, confirmation, determinism and counter-factuality.

According to Lange, there are several different stable sets: for example, the set of logical truths, the set of all physical laws and the set of all truths.

John Stuart Mill objected to the assertion that laws could have exceptions.

The problem of exceptions disappears when laws are understood as tendencies.

In any reasonably advanced science, there is really no such thing as an exception.

What is regarded as an exception to a principle is always another and different principle that interferes with the first principle: another force that acts on the first force and diverts it from its direction. There is not one law and one exception to this law.” Stanford Encyclopedia

Within our solar system, the movement of the solar planets is based on

- (1) their current position in space
- (2) their current motion inertia
- (3) their mass
- (4) the gravitational constant
- (5) their distance from the Sun and other planets.

Our assumption is that

The future position of a planet in space can only be determined by numerically adding the gravitational forces of the other planets and the Sun step by step and calculating the next position of all planets in a giant iteration loop.

NASA’s JPL Horizon Model works differently. The best way to understand NASA’s solar system model is to read Paul Schlyter’s essays and excels on the WEB. Our approach is a kind of hybrid: we study the planetary orbital trends provided by NASA.

Our total time horizon is less than 100 million years.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

65 million years ago, the Mexico meteorite wiped out the dinosaurs.

5 million years ago, our ancestors began to use stones and sticks and to walk upright.

Compared to this history, 250,000 years in astronomy is the blink of an eye.

We assume that the G constant does not change.

We assume that none of the planetary orbits are stable forever.

We assume that the masses of the Sun and the planets do not change dramatically.

We assume that the orbits of the planets do not change places instantaneously.

We have shown the development of the orbit of Mars between 1850 and 2050.

We have analyzed the forces exerted by the Sun and the seven planets on the orbits of Mars:

(A) Drift of the Martian perihelia towards the Sun.

(B) Increasing – decreasing the speed of the Martian orbit.

(C) Increase – decrease in the inclination of Mars relative to the plane of the Sun.

With (C) we have to pass. – The angle of attack of the gravitational forces of the other planet on the inclination of Mars is very small. – We also believe that we need to know more about the contribution of the Sun before we can assess the reasons for the Martian tilt.

SAMAC's RPVM algorithms of SAMAC provide the following results:

The PACUs on a daily basis between the Sun and Mars can be accumulated.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

The NASA ephemeris tables between 1850 and 2050 show that the sum of the measured solar and planetary absolute PACUs pulling the perihelion of Mars closer to the Sun is increasing.

This proves that there is no reversal of the Mars perihelion trend.

The orbit of Mars will cross the orbit of Earth in about 250,000 years.

At the same time, we measure that the planets and the Sun as a whole contribute to the speed of the Martian orbit in a microscopic way.

These observations show that, *ceteris paribus*,

there will be no serious reversal of gravitational forces, as Mars is experiencing today.

IX. The correct Solution for the N-Body Problem

A formula generally refers to an equation that relates one expression to another.

An analytic formula is a mathematical expression that consists of known operations that can be easily calculated. Below is a list of simple mathematical functions.

Area of a square: a^2

Perimeter of a square: $4 * a$

Circumference of a circle: $2\pi * r$

$$d = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2}$$

Distance Formula

The formula for calculating the forces between two objects in space is nice and simple.

F = gravitational force between 2 objects in space. – G = gravitational constant.

M = mass of the central body. – m = mass of the orbiting body. – R = distance from M to m .

In physics, the n-body problem is the problem of predicting the individual motions of a group of celestial bodies interacting with each other through gravity.

There is no simple arithmetic solution to the n-body problem.

“Solving the N-body problem is motivated by the desire to understand the movements of the sun, moon and planets.” WIKIPEDIA

“The N-body problem is the age-old physics challenge of predicting the motion of N individual bodies interacting with each other under gravity.” Portillo, Dierickx

“A long-standing problem in the study of the solar system was that Mercury's orbit did not behave as required by Newton's equations.” – One of the cornerstones of modern physics. Paul Gerber, in 1898 and 1902, and Albert Einstein in 1905 and 1916 arrived at an identical mathematical solution to explain the sum of Mercury's perihelia over 100 years.

arithmetic: $\epsilon = 24 * \pi^3 * \frac{a^2}{T^2 * c^2 * (1 - e^2)}$ **bad, false, wrong!**

The geniuses don't specify when a 100-year period of Mercury's precession begins or ends.

Who made their assumption "... did not behave as required by Newton's equations"?

The Mercury problem – if there is a problem at all – is an n-body problem.

What scientist can say with a clear conscience that Newton doesn't work for Mercury?

Have scientists ever been caught lying or murdering?

Ignaz Semmelweis, 1818-1865, was a Hungarian physician. He discovered bacteria and infections. Semmelweis was harassed by his fellow doctors and taken to an insane asylum. Semmelweis died there after 2 weeks.

Robert Koch discovered the tuberculosis pathogen in 1882. – Koch developed the supposed cure tuberculin. When hundreds of his patients died, he embarked on a scientific journey until the bad press had died down. – In 1905, Koch was awarded the Nobel Prize for Medicine.

Astrophysical N-body problems can only be solved with precise data and software algorithms.

NASA's ephemeris tables are limited to about 100,000 rows.

The minimum time steps of the position and velocity of the solar planets are 1 minute.

NASA astronomers use the Python programming language with a precision of 15 float.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

SAMAC has discovered a Microsoft genius. His add-ins offer unlimited accuracy.

SAMAC would like to incorporate this accuracy into NASA's SSD application.

This process would require JPL's approval and cooperation.

SAMAC proves that improving NASA's ephemeris data leads to major scientific advances.

Hans Lippershey called his telescope a Kijker – a seer - in 1608. It magnified an image up to three times. Others claimed that he had stolen the design from Zacharias Jansen, another glassmaker. – Jacob Metius applied for a patent for a telescope a few weeks after Lippershey.

1610 Galileo published a scientific work based on observations made through a telescope.

One of Galileo's first telescopes had a linear magnification of 8 to 10 times. Galileo aimed the new invention at the night sky. – Galileo reported that he saw at least ten times more stars through the telescope than were visible to the naked eye.

"I concluded from this and decided without hesitation that there are three stars in the sky that move around Jupiter, like Venus and Mercury around the sun." Galileo Galilei

In 1627 Kepler published his great Rudolphine Tables. Kepler's corrections reduced the maximum position errors for Mars by an order of magnitude, from almost 5° to about 0.5° .

Kepler had corrected Tycho Brahe's great Martian catastrophe.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

The NASA Mars ephemeris tables can be improved from 1 minute to 5-second increments. This 12-fold increase in accuracy clears the fog around the behavior of the Martian perihelia. SAMAC uses the same Newtonian-based software algorithms to determine the position of Mercury in the perihelion region in 1-second increments. – The standard model of physics uses an inaccurate 100-year estimate of Mercury’s precession. – SAMAC’s Newtonian algorithms debunk a 150-year-old Mercury mystery invented by Urbain-Jean Le Verrier.

Amount (arcsec/Julian century)	Cause
531.63" ±0.69	Gravitational tugs of the other planets
0.0254"	Oblateness of the Sun (quadrupole moment)
42.98" ±0.04	General relativity
574.64" ±0.69	Total
574.10" ±0.65	Observed

Any person with two brain cells will ask themselves: “Beginning of observations? – End?”

How on earth would these shaman physicists know the state of the planets?

Computers – as we know them – are only a few decades old. – Radar analysis of the planets reached its current state when humans were able to send space probes to the seven planets.

To get this kind of information, all you have to do is the following:

Download the NASA ephemeris tables from the Internet.

Improve NASA’s accuracy from 1 minute to 1 second.

Use MS Excel to customize Your presentation.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

SAMAC looks forward to sharing our solutions with the world of science.

	A	B	C	D	E	I	R	S	T
1	G (N·m ² /kg ²) =	6,674255E-11	M (kg) =	1,98875E+30					
2									
3	t (sec)	X (m)	Y (m)	Z (m)	Distance	V (m/s)	$F = -G \frac{Mm}{r^2}$ $s = \frac{a}{2} \cdot t^2 + v_0 \cdot t + s_0$		
4									
5	0	10.101.031.200	44.795.218.078	2.734.200.369	46.001.285.260,7899	58.976,3405585			
223	218	10.088.542.410	44.797.948.516	2.735.569.028	46.001.284.950,3126	58.976,3408888			
224	219	10.088.485.120	44.797.961.034	2.735.575.306	46.001.284.950,2994	58.976,3408888			
225	220	10.088.427.831	44.797.973.552	2.735.581.584	46.001.284.950,2990	58.976,3408888	*Perihelion		
226	221	10.088.370.541	44.797.986.070	2.735.587.862	46.001.284.950,3116	58.976,3408888			
227	222	10.088.313.252	44.797.998.588	2.735.594.140	46.001.284.950,3371	58.976,3408887			
228	223	10.088.255.962	44.798.011.106	2.735.600.417	46.001.284.950,3754	58.976,3408887			

Ignore the prophecies of Le Verrier. Trust the Excel of the 21st century and the observations of NASA. You recognize the details of Mercury's precession and retrograde precession.

NASA's Mercury ephemeris shows the scientific world what to do next.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

Numbers do not lie. – The scientific truth will come to light sooner or later.

The standard model of physics is more of a cult, with no relation to reality and science.

Proof of Relativity – NO!

Paul Gerber

$$\Psi = 24\pi^3 \frac{a^2}{\tau^2 c^2 (1 - e^2)}$$

1898

Einstein

$$\epsilon = 24\pi^3 \frac{a^2}{T^2 c^2 (1 - e^2)}$$

1915

The NASA SSD ephemeris tables show that for each different start time of the “100 years” a completely different sum is observed for the cumulative precession numbers.

since 1850	Orbit #	Perihelion on	NASA	since 1850	Orbit #	Perihelion on	NASA
from 002	04/25/1850	581,38	from 168	04/18/1890	582,92	from 334	04/12/1930
to 416	01/11/1950		to 582	01/04/1990		to 748	12/27/2029
from 044	06/06/1860	561,82	from 210	05/31/1900	564,66	from 376	05/24/1940
to 458	02/22/1960		to 624	02/15/2000		to 790	02/08/2040
from 085	04/22/1870	561,26	from 251	04/16/1910	575,70	from 417	04/09/1950
to 499	01/07/1970		to 665	12/31/2009		to 831	12/24/2049

Both – Paul Gerber and Albert Einstein arrive at a simple arithmetic formula.

If there were a Mercury precession problem, it would be an n-body problem.

As the world of science knows, there is no simple arithmetic solution to an n-body problem.

The sum of Mercury’s accumulated precessions depends on which start date is chosen.

X. The Pioneer Anomaly – see IEEE Spectrum

The Pioneer 10 and Pioneer 11 probes gave mankind the first close-up images of worlds beyond the asteroid belt of the solar system. – They also left behind a secret.

Both probes flew close to Jupiter, which led to changes in their trajectories. In the case of Pioneer 11, the navigators used the giant planet's gravity to deliberately hurl the probe past Saturn. As the probes flew on, their trajectories became straighter and straighter.

A group of researchers led by astronomer John D. Anderson at NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) has set out to use the navigation data from these mostly passive probes to make high-precision measurements of the gravitational environment of the outer solar system.

Taking the JPL Solar Ephemeris Tables to the next Level

From 1980 onwards, Anderson and his colleagues noticed a considerable deviation in the predicted trajectories of the spacecraft. – The discrepancy was not random noise.

The accuracy of the navigation model could be restored when a small, constant, sunward force was applied to the spacecraft. There was evidence that the thermal recoil force was underestimated. Accurate calculation of the thermal forces was difficult because it required telemetry recordings of the spacecraft temperatures and a detailed thermal model, neither of which were available. – All thermal models predicted a decrease in the effect over time, which did not occur.

WIKIPEDIA

Banal causes include conventional effects that were overlooked or incorrectly modeled in the original analysis, such as measurement errors, thrust due to gas leakage or uneven heat radiation. A "new physics" explanation has proposed a revision of gravitational physics.

Gas leaks from the spacecraft's generators – RTGs – have been considered a possible cause.

The possibility of observational errors, which include measurement and calculation errors, has been cited as a reason for interpreting the data as an anomaly. – It is possible, but not proven, that this anomaly is related to the flyby anomaly that has been observed in other spacecrafts.

WIKIPEDIA

This SAMAC paper points out miscalculations that are overlooked by most scientists.

Every beginner and his dogs know that n-body problems cannot be solved with simple arithmetic formulas. – The correct calculation of the trajectory is complex. – Any error along the way can lead to huge discrepancies in the results. – At this point, we assume that most of the JPL measurements of solar and planetary masses and orbits are pretty good.

There is one obvious flaw in JPL's SSD number processing that stands out.

Floating point calculation, as used in the JPL programming language Python, gives poor results when small amounts often need to be added to large numbers. – There are simple ways to increase Python's floating-point limit from (15) to, say, (60).

XI. SUMMARY

JPL Solar System Dynamics explains the nature and future of our solar system.

SAMAC has shown that the orbit of Mars has a drift of 400 km per orbit.

NASA's ephemeris tables prove that (A) there is no change in the “ceteris paribus” scenarios and (B) the main cause of the Martian drift is that the Sun is pulling the perihelia of Mars closer to the Sun.

The change in the inclinations of Mars and Earth is not entirely clear.

A larger angle between the inclinations – tilts – of the two planets would increase the angle of attack when the two planets collide. – The ACUs show how tiny the gravitational acceleration is compared to the gigantic masses and speeds. Cosmic masses float like weightless jellyfish.

The ACU of a body near the surface of planet Earth is 9.81 m / s^2 .

The ACUs of the Sun on the planets are:

m/s^2	Mercury	Venus	Earth	Mars	Jupiter	Saturn	Uranus	Neptune
ACU Perihelion	0,0627	0,0115	0,0061	0,0031	0,000242	0,000068	0,000021	0,000007
ACU Aphelion	0,0272	0,0112	0,0057	0,0021	0,000199	0,000059	0,000015	0,000006

An infinite amount of mass in the universe will not lead to a gravitational collapse of the universe. – The distances between objects in the universe dampen gravitational forces.

PACUs are artificial new indicators that measure the gravitational effect of multiple, chaotically rotating planets around a central massive object. – Over time, the perihelion of Mars will cross the orbit of the planet Earth. – We have shown that the solar PACUs continue to accumulate over time. The perihelion of Mars' orbit will get closer and closer to Earth's orbit over time and eventually cross it. – There are a number of dramatic scenarios to which a convergence of Mars and Earth could lead. – The gravitational pull of Jupiter and the inner planets will not change dramatically. Their masses will remain the same, as will their orbits. NASA JPL's Horizons system will take astrophysics to the next level.

XII. Credits

We have marked references to the owners of the images and knowledge snippets.

Pixabay and Shutterstock were great sources of inspiration.

WIKIPEDIA is the free encyclopedia we studied, well beyond our citations.

We tried to track down David Fox, to whom we are indebted for his Newton Excel template.

Some of our text most likely comes from a source that is currently unknown to us.

If anyone believes that they have the rights to the texts we present here, we will be happy to acknowledge their claims and add their name to the list of credits.

Our greatest thanks go to NASA and JPL for providing the treasure trove of solar data,
astronomical images and knowledge.

This white paper has been improved by AI – Instatext.

XIII. Frequently asked questions

Q: Why haven't all the other experts already solved the problem you're discussing here?

A: “The Motivation Opportunity Ability – MOA – framework offers three ways to question the action or inaction of a person or group.” Arts Managed

“Motivation describes the individual's willingness to act. Opportunity represents the environmental or contextual mechanisms that enable action. Ability represents the person's skills or knowledge associated with the action. Rothschild, 1999.” ScienceDirect

“Motivation drives us to act in ways that bring us closer to our goals.” Very Well Mind

“Positive goals are the pursuit of success. Negative goals are the avoidance of failure.” ACCA

“To create something new, you have to change or combine objects, which ultimately destroys the object you started with.” Medium

“An opportunity is a chance to do something.” Cambridge Dictionary

“In 1610, Galileo Galilei discovered four moons orbiting the planet Jupiter with his [brand new } telescope. When he looked at what he thought was a group of stars, he noticed that the objects appeared to move in a regular pattern [around Jupiter].” National Geographic

“Kepler used simple math to formulate three laws of planetary motion. Kepler's first law states that the planets move in elliptical orbits around the sun. He also discovered that the planets move proportionally faster when they're closer to the sun.” NASA

SAMAC's motivation is to make money. SAMAC is the first to discover orbital drift.

SAMAC's opportunity is that no one else has discovered this phenomenon yet.

SAMAC is able to download NASA's ephemeris tables into Excel spreadsheets.

Most physicists and astronomers seem to have neither the motivation nor the skills to do this.

NASA's ephemerides tables are radar based. SAMAC uses improved software algorithms.

SAMAC combines radar-based NASA observations with modern computer technology.

Above all, humanity must find solutions to avoid the Earth-Colusion Prophecy.